

Background: Wearable sensor technology offers significant potential for continuous respiratory monitoring across various domains, including clinical diagnostics, sports performance analysis, and occupational health. Traditional methods for measuring respiratory rate, such as spirometry and capnography, require stationary equipment, limiting their usability in dynamic environments. Inertial measurement units (IMUs) provide an alternative by capturing subtle body movements associated with breathing. This study explores the feasibility of classifying breathing movements using IMU data from sensor placed on the abdomen.

Objective: The primary objective of this study is to develop and evaluate a machine learning model capable of distinguishing between respiratory movements and noise using IMU sensor data. We hypothesize that a multi-input convolutional neural network (1D-CNN) can accurately classify breathing patterns based on time-series sensor data.

Methods: The dataset consists of 53 participants who performed a static breathing test (controlled deep and normal breathing). One Bosch BNO085 IMUs were used to record linear acceleration and absolute orientation at 330 Hz. The recorded signals were preprocessed and labeled into two classes: Breathing (from the static test) and Noise (from walking activities). A multi-input 1D-CNN was trained, where each sensor feature was processed separately through individual convolutional branches before merging into a fully connected classification layer. Performance was evaluated using stratified K-fold cross-validation.

Results: The model achieved an accuracy of approximately 80 % and an AUC of 0.76. However, the confusion matrix indicates a moderate rate of false positives, suggesting that some segments labeled as noise may contain genuine respiratory patterns. This labeling issue likely arises because participants continued breathing naturally during walking activity, leading to an overlap between the two classes.

Implication for research and/or (healthcare) practice: The findings demonstrate the feasibility of using IMU sensors for respiratory monitoring but highlight the need for improved data labeling and model refinement. Future work should focus on optimizing preprocessing techniques, exploring alternative architectures such as LSTM or Transformer models, and incorporating additional validation methods. Addressing the labeling issue is crucial for improving classification accuracy, particularly in dynamic conditions. The study lays the foundation for real-world applications of wearable IMU-based respiratory monitoring in healthcare and performance assessment.